

METHODOLOGY OF TEACHING MUSIC TO ELEMENTARY SCHOOL STUDENTS WITH DISABILITIES.

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Abstract: In this article, the proposals and recommendations developed in connection with the methodology of teaching music to students of boarding school elementary school with disabilities and additional information on this topic are presented.

Key words: lesson, practice, exhibition, tradition, music, troupe, instrument, style, song, composer, conservatory, score.

All that is taught in school to educate the young generation to be mature in all aspects music culture lessons, which are part of education of sophistication, among subjects is of great importance. Music expresses human feelings, dreams and desires in its own artistic language is enough. Music is another subject at school has a direct impact on learning. Music as a living art form is a time, life, it reflects nature and human feelings and desires. Makes him happy and married and protects from life. Grandfather of our national culture Abu Nasir Al-Farabi said, "This science is beneficial for the body." Our grandfather Shaykh Sa'di "Music is the companion of the human soul. Therefore, we teach music, help we need to use grade school students. Because there is music in the social class at school The foundation of the doctrine is poured. The main goal of teaching music in primary school is the primary grade to teach students the ability to study music based on the laws of beauty and to provide them with a musical culture. Musical culture in primary grades lessons, an integral part of the moral-aesthetic education system of general education boMib is considered.

Teaching music in elementary grades is the following task!

makes:

- 1.0 to instill in students a love of music and a sense of rhythm Cultivation of musical learning memory, formation of attention and artistic taste;
2. The feeling of love for our national music heritage and through it for the Motherland in students to educate;
3. To develop artistic creativity in students. 0 to develop students' ability to see beauty and bring beauty into life.

Listening to music is of great importance in enriching the impression of the musical creativity of our students and expanding their imagination. From the beginning to the end of the music listening lesson is realized, because all types of activities of music culture lessons (singing, performing musical rhythmic movements, listening to music) created in musical sounds expressed through tone. Music culture lessons for elementary school students to be able to perceive the beautiful things around and to form a spiritual outlook serves. All subjects based on "State Educational Standards for Primary Education". as well as a music program was developed. Our national music in the content of the new program full use of its heritage, popular folk songs and songs, lapar, epics and today's modern music are reflected. The main theme of my program is "Music and Life" year, It is subordinated to the theme of the quarter, lesson topics, and the year, and is logically integrated into one content constitutes a whole.

In order to conduct lessons in the content of the new program, the music teacher has his own it is necessary to improve his musical-theoretical knowledge, because it is important to raise the interest of my students in music lessons, to educate the young generation in the spirit of love for the Motherland, and The teacher is considered to be the leader in bringing up a spiritual and enlightened student. Everyone knows that not every artist can teach music at school.

She devoted herself to her profession and her children to become a primary school music teacher a highly cultured and broad-minded person should have a good mind. It is pedagogy, it is necessary to have in-depth knowledge in practical fields of psychology, physiology of paints. The scope of activity of a music teacher in primary grades is wide. Musical culture along with his lessons, he should also organize and manage types of music education outside the classroom.

It is the responsibility of the elementary school teacher to hold open educational hours outside the classroom, to conduct public and group forms of music education. This includes "Independence Day", "Knowledge Day", "Teachers' Day", "Alphabet Day", "New yil", "Nowruz holiday", meetings with painter poets and artists. Elementary music in solving educational problems in today's independence the teacher keeps pace with the times, information technology and advanced pedagogy it is necessary to fully develop technological skills and organize the education and training process based on them.

The main goal of teaching music in the first grade is to instill interest in music among students and composition of musical impressions, conscious perception of music as art. As a result children develop the basic principles of observing music. This to achieve the goal, the following tasks are performed;

1. To develop students' musical abilities and musical education.
2. Developing the ability to perceive music (listening).
3. Improve singing skills.
4. Ethical and aesthetic education through musical artistic and ideological content.

It is known that music is a reflection of life and times. That's why in primary classes The main theme of the program of music lessons is "Music and life". Conducting music culture lessons in primary school based on children's life experiences It is important as an educational tool. Because singing and listening in the program recommended songs and musical works for, happy childhood, humanitarianism, Homeland consists of works about love, love for nature.

Children's music in the first grade the knowledge acquired through character images is relative and turns into concrete (concrete) concepts in the next classes. Also, the knowledge acquired for the first time at the beginning of the school year in the first grade is called the pre-note period.

Tasks related to the first types of musical activity constitute the content of the work. This is it Musical activities include singing, listening to music, musical literacy, performing dance elements Houses, stepping, accompanying children's musical instruments, play an important role in the formation of musical culture. Singing in a choir in first grade as a team activity It is carried out with the direct participation of students. Singing is complex psychological and is a physiological process. Nerve cells in the brain are actively involved in this, positive in students provides the activity of senses, the chest is a sound-producing organ of articulation activates respiratory organs and creates conditions for effective work of students.

To teach singing in elementary grades, this song is listened to and then the song is taught based on the teaching method:

1. A short introduction by the teacher about the song (about the author of the song, about the historical or educational significance of the song, a short story, interesting facts about this song conducting life interviews and showing pictures).
2. Full performance of the song by the teacher.
3. The musical character of the song, its means of expression, form, genre with students joint identification.
4. Teaching the song into musical sentences.
5. Work on the performance qualities of the song (breath, pure intonation, pronunciation, dynamic signs based expressive singing).
6. Conducting a short conversation (question-and-answer) about their impressions, visual materials based on.

Elementary school students cannot focus on something for a long time, they get tired very quickly. That is why in music culture classes it is necessary to pay attention to the musical performance, use gentle movements such as clapping,

stepping. Especially the paints are musical instruments (circle, tambourine, rattle, maracas, three performing accompaniment and rhythmic dance movements on the corner, rumba, drum, boyalami activates and the lesson is interesting and meaningful.

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